

Figure 10: 8- and 16-cornered temple base, MY 5.90-91 and MY comm 5.90-91.

To make an 8-cornered design from a square one:

A square, abcd, is made. The diagonal ad is measured. $1/16^{\text{th}}$ is subtracted from it to give a length $ad - 1/16^{\text{th}}$. Arcs with a radius of $ad - 1/16^{\text{th}}$ are drawn around the corners a, b, c and d. The points of intersection of those arcs indicate 4 more corners that are each $1/2ad$ from the centre of the *kṣetra*.

To make a 16-cornered design from an 8-cornered one, method 1:

Use a string that is the length eg to draw arcs around each corner, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h. The points of intersection of those arcs indicate 8 more corners.

To make a 16-cornered design from an 8-cornered one, method 2:

A string that is $2/3(ad - 1/16^{\text{th}})$ is used to make arcs around the corners a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h. The points of intersection of those arcs indicate 8 more corners.